

CERTIFICATE

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RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALIDA

NUCLEAR MEANS OF EXPRESSING THE LEXICO-SEMANTIC FIELD "HAPPINESS" IN SYSTEMS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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2023/APREL